

Mapping Engineering Education Research in Europe

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Context

The growth of Engineering Education Research (EER) has led to claims about it becoming a globally connected field of inquiry. Following from this, recent studies have employed scientometric data drawn from SCOPUS to provide insights into the research careers of EER practitioners in parts of Europe: Portugal, Spain and the Nordic countries. Within the SEFI EER SIG, ongoing work by the workshop organisers is studying how national contexts influence the EER output in the various European countries.

Workshop Aims

1. To share with participants scientometric data on EER publication output and research careers across the countries of Europe;
2. To guide participants to situate this scientometric data in the light of their knowledge of their own institutional and national context and to compare international contexts;
3. To learn new insights from participants that broaden the base of relevant EER data from across Europe. This could lead to future work in which the findings are explored in relation to the contextual factors associated with each of the geographical regions, thus providing insight into ways to support development of EER in the future.

It is also hoped that its findings could also involve other stakeholders who could lobby for a parity of esteem between EER and engineering research (for career progression or promotion) both at national and European levels, and for more funding for EER by European research bodies.

Workshop structure

- Participant introduction activity
- Plenary session: presentation of scientometric data on EER publications and careers in European countries
- Group activity: participants work in international breakout groups to compare and contrast the EER landscapes in their respective countries
- Plenary session: reports back from group activity
- Wrap-up, including discussion on any follow-up to workshop

References

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